

High tibial osteotomy reduces compressive loads in the knee medial compartment and increases them in the lateral one during walking

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Abstract: High tibial osteotomy (HTO) is a well-accepted surgical procedure for patients with knee osteoarthritis (OA) and varus alignment aimed at realigning the tibia to reduce the load on the medial compartment of the knee. This study analyzed ambulatory knee loads – specifically the knee adduction moment and compressive forces – in patients before and 9 months after HTO by means of musculoskeletal modelling. HTO effectively reduces the knee adduction moment and unloads the medial knee compartment while increasing the compressive load on the lateral one. Musculoskeletal modelling contributes to the understanding of changes in knee compartmental loads due to load-altering interventions in patients with knee OA that goes beyond evidence gained from 3-dimensional motion capture and force data and inverse dynamics approaches.

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I. Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common type of arthritis or degenerative joint disease and occurs in a substantial portion of the population over the age of 50 [1]. The development of OA is often induced by altered joint mechanics that lead to increased or abnormal intra-articular forces. Variations in joint morphology and limb alignment can therefore represent a risk factor for the progression of OA, as in the case of varus alignment of the knee, which has been related to OA in the medial compartment [2].

High tibial osteotomy (HTO) is a well-accepted joint preserving surgical procedure for patients with knee OA and varus alignment aimed at realigning the tibia to reduce the load on the medial compartment of the knee presumably halting or slowing the rate of progression of the disease.

Gait analysis is a useful tool for assessing in vivo functional changes associated with knee pathology during activities such as walking. Ambulatory load – specifically the knee adduction moment as surrogate for the load distribution between the medial and lateral compartment of the knee – is known to play an important role in the initiation and progression of the disease [4,5]. Musculoskeletal modelling allows to estimate intra-articular joint loads in relation to individual motion patterns and musculoskeletal geometry, and hence represents a suitable tool for evaluating the effect of HTO on knee compartment load.

We hypothesized that HTO would reduce the knee adduction moment and the medial compartment compressive force while increasing the compressive load in the lateral compartment in a cohort of patients with medial knee OA.

II. Material and methods

Twelve patients (mean \pm 1SD, age: 45 \pm 9 years) diagnosed with isolated symptomatic medial compartment knee OA underwent opening wedge HTO. Kinematic (Vicon, UK) and kinetic (Kistler, Switzerland) data were recorded using the Plug-In Gait marker-set during 3D gait analysis sessions before (pre-) surgery as well as 9 \pm 3 months postoperatively.

The collected motion capture data was used as input for an inverse dynamics analysis (AnyBody Technology, Denmark) to evaluate external knee moments and knee contact forces. Personalized models were created from a generic lower limb model [3] scaled according to marker data from a static trial in an anatomic upright position. Knee varus/valgus alignment was estimated based on the position of knee-mounted skin markers during the static reference trial and implemented as a fixed change in the frontal plane orientation of the knee joint axis during all simulated gait cycles. The distribution of the compressive knee force across the medial and lateral compartments was evaluated through frontal plane static equilibrium equations as suggested by Stoltze et al. [6].

Differences between pre- and postoperative knee flexion angle and total knee contact forces were evaluated over the entire gait cycle through statistical parametric mapping (SPM) with two-tailed paired t-tests ($\alpha = 0.05$), while knee adduction moment, as well as medial and lateral knee compressive forces were analyzed with one-tailed paired t-tests ($\alpha = 0.05$) according to the stated hypotheses.

Figure 2: Mean \pm SD predicted knee flexion angle, external knee adduction moment, and total, medial, and lateral knee compressive forces in patients before (solid line) and after (dashed line) HTO. Phases of the gait cycle, for which a statistically significant difference in the SPM analysis was found, are indicated as grey bars below each subplot.

III. Results and discussion

Estimated mean varus knee alignment in the cohort was $7.2 \pm 3.7^\circ$ preoperatively and reduced to $1.3 \pm 3.2^\circ$ after HTO. The patients did not present any statistically significant difference in knee flexion angles after surgery. A statistically significant reduction in the postoperative external knee adduction moment was observed during mid and terminal stance leading to a reduction in the medial compartment compressive force during mid stance and an increase in lateral compartment compressive force during most of the stance phase. However, the total compressive load through the knee did not present any statistically significant difference.

IV. Conclusions

HTO effectively unloads the medial knee compartment by redistributing part of the overall compressive force to the

lateral compartment during gait. The timing of reductions in compressive force may not always coincide with the timing of reductions in knee adduction moments suggesting that the knee frontal moment may not adequately describe ambulatory load or changes induced by interventions at the compartment level. Future work should aim at further personalizing the models with morphological information from radiographic imaging and include the mechanical effect of soft tissue constraints at the knee, such as the collateral ligaments and the menisci, which would also enable a better characterization of all the forces acting within the knee [7].

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF #32003B_159871). Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: Informed consent has been obtained from all individuals included in this study. Ethical approval: The research related to human use complies with all the relevant national regulations, institutional policies and was performed in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration, and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

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